

Contents of Report

Separation Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study	LC-MS	Corresponding Email	juliette.jouhet@cea.fr
Document creation date	12/16/2024	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Targeted
Principal investigator	Juliette Jouhet	Clinical	No
Institution	Laboratoire de Physiologie Cellulaire et végétale -Platform Lipang		

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	No
pH adjustment	None	Special conditions	Freeze-drying of the sample prior to 5 min incubation in boiling ethanol to inactivate lipases
2-phase system	Folch	Derivatization	-

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium acetate	Ion source	ESI
Number of separation dimensions	One dimension	MS Level	MS2
Separation type 1	LC	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1.7
Separation mode 1 (liquid)	NP	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	Low resolution
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Resolution at MS2	Low
MS type	QQQ	Recording mode of raw data at MS2	Centroid mode
MS vendor	Agilent	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Extraction blank, Solvent blank, Internal standard blank	Type of QC sample	Reference material

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Precision	No
Lipid recovery	No	Accuracy	Yes
Dynamic quantification range	Yes	Guidelines followed	None
Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	No		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Available on request	Raw data upload	Available on request
Are metadata available?	Yes	Additional comments	-

Sample Descriptions

Plant / Plants / Cells

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	-80 °C
Provided preanalytical information	Time to freeze (min)	Additives	None
Temperature handling original sample	Room temperature	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Time to freeze (min)	0	Biobank samples	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	Yes		

Alga / Algae / Cells

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	-80 °C
Provided preanalytical information	Time to freeze (min)	Additives	None
Temperature handling original sample	Room temperature	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Time to freeze (min)	0	Biobank samples	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	Yes		

Media / culture medium / Other liquid material

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage temperature	-80 °C
Provided preanalytical information	Time to freeze (min)	Additives	None
Temperature handling original sample	Room temperature	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Time to freeze (min)	0	Biobank samples	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	Yes		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) DG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DG	Check on:	-
MS Level for identification	MS2	Limit of detection	No
Identification level	Species level	RT verified by standard	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Model for separation prediction	No
Fragments for identification		Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragment name			
-FA1(-H)-(H2O+NH3)			
-FA2(-H)-(H2O+NH3)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Which assumptions were presumed?	Fatty acids are present in the total extract measured by GC-MS	Further identification remarks	-

1) DG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Threshold 10x above lowest signal
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
DAG 18:0/22:6	-FA1(-H)- (H ₂ O+NH ₃)		
DAG 18:0/22:6	-FA2(-H)- (H ₂ O+NH ₃)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount and external standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.018242
Type I isotope correction	No		

2) DGDG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DGDG	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH ₄] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name			
	-HG(Hex2,341)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check on:	-		

2) DGDG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Threshold 10x above lowest signal
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
DAG 18:0/22:6	-FA1(-H)- (H ₂ O+NH ₃)		
DAG 18:0/22:6	-FA2(-H)- (H ₂ O+NH ₃)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount and external standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0182423
Type I isotope correction	No		

3) MGDG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	MGDG	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH ₄] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name			
	-HG(Hex, 179)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check on:	-		

3) MGDG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Threshold 10x above lowest signal
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
DAG 18:0/22:6	-FA1(-H)- (H2O+NH3)		
DAG 18:0/22:6	-FA2(-H)- (H2O+NH3)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount and external standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0182423
Type I isotope correction	No		

4) SQDG[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SQDG	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H] ⁻	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name			
HG(SQDG,225)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check on:	-		

4) SQDG[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Threshold 10x above lowest signal
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
SQDG 34:0	HG(SQDG,225)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount and external standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0182423
Type I isotope correction	No		

5) TG[M+NH4]+ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	Check on:	-
MS Level for identification	MS2	Limit of detection	No
Identification level	Species level	RT verified by standard	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4]+	Model for separation prediction	No
Fragments for identification		Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragment name			
-FA1(+HO)-(NH3)			
-FA2(+HO)-(NH3)			
-FA3(+HO)-(NH3)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Which assumptions were presumed?	Fatty acids are present in the total extract analysed by GC-MS	Further identification remarks	-

5) TG[M+NH4]+ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Threshold 10x above lowest signal
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s)	MS2	Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
DAG 18:0/22:6	-FA1(-H)- (H2O+NH3)		
DAG 18:0/22:6	-FA2(-H)- (H2O+NH3)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount and external standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0182423
Type I isotope correction	No		

6) CL[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CL	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name			
FA1(+O) + FA2(+O) + HG(GP)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check on:	-		

6) CL[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Threshold 10x above lowest signal
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
SQDG 34:0	HG(SQDG,225)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount and external standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0182423
Type I isotope correction	No		

7) PA[M+NH4]+ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PA	Limit of detection	Threshold 3x above lowest signal
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4]+	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name			
-H3PO4-H+NH4 (NL 115)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check on:	-		

7) PA[M+NH₄]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Threshold 10x above lowest signal
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
SQDG 34:0	HG (SQDG, 225)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount and external standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0182423
Type I isotope correction	No		

8) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Limit of detection	Threshold 3x above lowest signal
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name			
HG(PC,184)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check on:	-		

8) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Threshold 10x above lowest signal
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
SQDG 34:0	HG (SQDG, 225)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount and external standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0182423
Type I isotope correction	No		

9) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Limit of detection	Threshold 3x above lowest signal
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name			
-HG(PE,141)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check on:	-		

9) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Threshold 10x above lowest signal
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PE 36:0	-HG(PE,141)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount and external standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0182423
Type I isotope correction	No		

10) PG[M+NH₄]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PG	Limit of detection	Threshold 3x above lowest signal
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH ₄] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name			
-HG(PG,172+NH ₄)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check on:	-		

10) PG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Threshold 10x above lowest signal
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
SQDG 34:0	-HG (SQDG, 225)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount and external standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0182423
Type I isotope correction	No		

11) PI[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PI	Limit of detection	Threshold 3x above lowest signal
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor) ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name			
-HG(PI,260+NH4)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check on:	-		

11) PI[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Threshold 10x above lowest signal
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
SQDG 34:0	-HG (SQDG, 225)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount and external standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0182423
Type I isotope correction	No		

12) DGTS/A [M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DGTS/A	Limit of detection	Threshold 3x above lowest signal
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor) ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragment name			
-HG(DGTS/A, 236)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Background subtraction
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check on:	-		

12) DGTS/A [M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Threshold 10x above lowest signal
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
SQDG 34:0	_HG (SQDG, 225)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount and external standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0182423
Type I isotope correction	No		